

A Review on Audiological Management of Early Childhood Hearing Loss

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 04 July 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Audiological Management Early Childhood Hearing Loss Behavioral Observation Audiometry Visual Reinforcement Audiometry Otoacoustic Emissions Auditory Brainstem Response Pure-Tone Audiometry Sensorineural hearing Loss</p>	<p>Hearing loss in early childhood can significantly impede speech, language, cognitive, and emotional development. Childhood hearing loss carries a significant burden, with serious consequences for the affected children and substantial economic impact. Unfortunately, in many developing countries, there is limited focus on initiatives that support early identification, intervention, and rehabilitation for these children. Timely audiological management during these developing years is crucial in minimizing long-term effects. There are ranges of audiological assessment tools available for detecting hearing loss in children, emphasizing their appropriateness across different developmental stages, infancy toddlerhood, preschool, and school-age. At the neonatal stage, objective tools like tympanometry help to assess the integrity of the middle ear functions. For infants and toddlers, Behavioral Observation Audiometry (BOA) and Visual Reinforcement Audiometry (VRA) assessments are conducted which is vital for timely intervention and provide valuable observations when used alongside other methods then complemented by Otoacoustic Emissions (OAE) and Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR) test. As children mature into preschool and school-age years, more interactive assessments, including Conditioned Play Audiometry and Speech Audiometry can be used and provide helpful results. Standard Pure-Tone Audiometry (PTA) can be done after five years or sooner if the child can participate. Hearing loss is classified as sensorineural, conductive, or mixed. Sensorineural hearing loss is the most prevalent type among newborns, depending on the underlying cause with approximately 50% of cases attributed to genetic factors. In contrast, acquired hearing loss often arises from infectious illnesses particularly meningitis neurological trauma, exposure to excessively loud noises, or the use of ototoxic medications. This review underscores the need to review current strategies and audiological management of early childhood hearing loss.</p>

1. Introduction

Early childhood hearing loss refers to a significant reduction in hearing sensitivity detected in infants and young children, often defined as a hearing threshold exceeding 30 dB HL in the better ear before the age of 15 years. It encompasses sensorineural, conductive, or mixed loss, and can be either congenital, present at birth or acquired during early life. Permanent hearing loss can occur at any age but about 25% of the current burden is of a childhood onset (Tobih et al., 2013). Again about 798,000 babies worldwide suffer from permanent hearing loss at birth or within the neonatal period and at least 90% of them are in developing countries (Ikeda, Murray, & Salomon, 2009). This condition is notably common, affecting approximately one to three per 1,000 newborns and increasing to about six per 1,000 by school age (Banda & Nakstad, 2021). Furthermore, Hearing loss is prevalently affecting about one to three per thousand newborns in the general population and two to four per 1,000 in infants with risk factors (Watkin & Baldwin 2011). The global population affected by disabling hearing loss has increased significantly, rising from 42 million in 1985 to 360 million by 2010. Among them, 7.5 million were children under the age of five. More recent figures indicate a continued rise, with approximately 466 million people currently experiencing disabling hearing impairment. Recent data from 2015, nearly 500 million individuals equating to roughly 6.8% of the global population were living with significant hearing impairment, and this figure is expected to rise in the future. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2011) reports that more than 34 million children below the age of fifteen are affected by disabling hearing impairment. Diagnosing early childhood hearing loss requires consideration of factors such as the suspected cause, type, degree, side of the loss, age of onset, and any additional factors like exposure to excessive loud noise.

2. Prevalence of Early Childhood Hearing Loss

Hearing loss is more common in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), often due to factors like higher rates of infectious diseases such as

maternal rubella, and the use of ototoxic medications. Unfortunately, many children in Africa are diagnosed late. A 2018 study in Botswana revealed that the median age for initial referral to the main audiology clinic was as high as 6-7 years, highlighting a significant delay in detection and intervention (Burke, Shenton, & Taylor, 2012).

Effective primary prevention is rarely possible in children with congenital hearing loss, especially in developing nations (Tobih et al., 2013). Nonetheless, such infants can develop essential language and cognitive skills if the condition is detected early and they are provided with appropriate intervention services within the first year of life (Olusanya et al., 2008). Many of these forms of hearing loss, can be prevented or managed through public health initiatives, genetic counseling and through early hearing detection and intervention. In developing countries, infant hearing loss has been referred to as a silent epidemic because despite its widespread prevalence, it is not detected by routine clinical examination and without appropriate screening, caregivers may not even be aware (Adedayo et al., 2014).

By so doing, most developed countries have implemented Universal Newborn Hearing Screening (UNHS) to ensure early identification and timely intervention of early childhood hearing loss. Despite the success of these screening programs, ongoing surveillance remains necessary due to the possibility of hearing changes during early childhood. When prevention is not possible, both the Joint Committee on Infant Hearing (JCIH) and the World Health Organization emphasize the importance of early hearing detection and intervention. Such programs typically ensure that children have access to comprehensive hearing and language development support by six months of age.

3. The Need for Hearing Screening In Managing Early Childhood Hearing Loss

World Health Organization Recommendation 27 advocates for the worldwide adoption of Universal Newborn Hearing Screening. The main goal of Universal Newborn Hearing Screening is to identify hearing loss in infants early, (JCIH, 2019). Universal Newborn Hearing Screening (UNHS) programs started being introduced in the early 1990s. Research showed that these initiatives led to earlier detection of hearing impairment, and timely enrollment in early intervention programs. These advancements were found to significantly enhance developmental outcomes during early childhood (Nelson, Bougatsos, & Nygren, 2008).

The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force supports universal newborn hearing screening to detect hearing loss early and promote proper language development. This strategic hearing assessment process leads to quicker referral, diagnosis, and intervention compared to targeted screening. Studies show children screened early have better language outcomes by school age. Targeted screening misses up to 50% of cases, often due to late-onset hearing loss or lack of risk factors. Routine screening by healthcare professionals is crucial to ensure early identification and care (JCIH, 2000).

Unfortunately, newborn hearing screening has not yet been universally adopted, particularly in rural areas of developing nations where there is a shortage of essential hearing assessment equipment. In addition, lack of parental awareness in these regions about the importance of early hearing assessments likely contributes to these shortcomings. As a result, these factors pose major obstacles to achieving the intended goals. Therefore, in areas where such screening programs are not yet in place, it is important to ensure the availability of hearing assessment tools and to improve parents' understanding and awareness of the potential consequences of delayed diagnosis (Patel & Feldman, 2011).

4. Early Behavioral Assessment Measures

Behavioral Observation Audiometry (BOA), Pure Tone Audiometry (PTA), and Speech Audiometry are essential tools in managing childhood hearing loss. BOA involves observing infants' behavioral responses to sound and is used for children between 6 and 24 months although it lacks precision (Northern & Downs, 2014). Pure Tone Audiometry is the gold standard for quantifying hearing thresholds in older, cooperative children, offering detailed information on the type and degree of hearing loss (ASHA, 2005). Speech audiometry assesses speech detection, discrimination, and recognition, helping to evaluate functional hearing and guide hearing aid fitting. Together, these tests inform accurate diagnosis, intervention, and rehabilitation strategies to support speech and language developments. Other children mostly from ages 2 to 5, are conditioned also undergo Visual Reinforcement Audiometry (VRA), which requires them to sit unassisted and turn their head toward sound sources while wearing earphones, with visual reinforces placed at each side. Sound stimuli are delivered at various frequencies and intensities. Play Audiometry (CPA) is used, where children respond to sounds through playful activities like placing a peg or ball in response to tones presented through headphones.

5. Electroacoustic Measures

Tympanometry, an objective electroacoustic test assesses middle ear function by measuring eardrum mobility in response to air pressure changes. It is crucial in managing hearing loss in children, especially those too young for reliable behavioral testing. The test helps detect middle ear effusion, Eustachian tube dysfunction, and tympanic membrane perforations, which are common causes of conductive hearing loss in children. Tympanometry is quick, non-invasive, and provides immediate results, enabling early diagnosis and intervention. Moreover, another electroacoustic measure like Otoacoustic emission test (OAE), is the most frequently utilized method in newborn hearing assessments since it is simple, safe, and fast to do, and serves as a reliable indicator of potential hearing loss. This test is especially convenient for newborns, who tend to be less active than older infants, often eliminating the need for sedation during the procedure. If the infant does not pass the OAE screening or shows signs suggestive of hearing loss, ABR test should be conducted before the baby reaches three months of age. Considering these two audiological measures they help operate base on constellation of clinical findings that suggest normal function on some cochlear structures and abnormal functioning of the VIIIth nerve and brainstem (Brad, 2010). Unlike other type of sensorineural loss where Otoacoustic Emission and ABR are likely to be abnormal, auditory neuropathy is characterized by normal OAE results and significantly abnormal ABR responses, even when measured with very loud sounds. (Ogundiran, 2020).

6. Electrophysiological Measures

The Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR) test, an electrophysiological instrument, objectively measures the auditory nerve and brainstem response to sound, helping determine both hearing thresholds and neural integrity. ABR plays a critical role in diagnosing conditions like sensorineural hearing loss and auditory neuropathy. It is commonly used following failed OAE newborn hearing screenings to confirm the presence and degree of hearing loss (JCIH, 2019). It has proven to be both effective and economical in detecting and determining the extent and nature of hearing loss in newborns (Lawrensia & Gomez Pomar, 2023). More recently, interest has shifted toward the Auditory Steady-State Response (ASSR), also an advance electrophysiological test which uses modulated tones, that are less affected by sleep state, it a reliable option in infants. These tests approach enhances the precision of threshold estimation and supports early diagnosis and timely intervention. Again, it measures the brain's response to sound stimuli delivered through insert earphones, headphones or a bone conduction transducer, depending on the testing method. ASSR typically uses frequency-specific tones commonly at 500, 1000, 2000, and 4000Hz to estimate hearing thresholds. ASSR also plays a major role in choosing candidate for Cochlear Implantation as with the help of it, we can easily determine if the residual hearing is within or under the speech banana on Audiogram and if hearing aid provides limited benefits after trial.

7. Aural Rehabilitation

A coordinated approach like an Early Hearing Detection and Intervention (EHDI) system that links healthcare with early learning services is essential to support the overall growth and success of children with hearing loss. When built on solid evidence, these systems can lessen the long-term challenges associated with hearing loss and lead to better developmental outcomes for affected children (Yoshinaga-Itano et al., 2021). Such programs help address and promote equal opportunities among children who are deaf or hard of hearing (DHH).

When hearing loss is determined to be permanent or not amenable to treatment, amplification options such as hearing aids should be included in the care plan, regardless of whether the loss is sensorineural, conductive, or mixed. These intervention services involve selecting the appropriate hearing aids particularly for children with bilateral sensorineural hearing loss as well as cochlear implants. These are typically combined with specialized auditory training, in which sign language instruction plays an essential role, (Rovers et al., 2004). Even mild hearing deficits can hinder speech and language acquisition, making early amplification essential (Tharpe, 2008). Infants diagnosed with permanent sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) through UNHS should receive hearing aids by six months and be monitored for speech and language development. If hearing aids provide little benefit in cases of severe to profound SNHL, cochlear implantation is advised. Advances in hearing assessment and improved speech outcomes have allowed implantation in select cases with additional issues, such as inner ear malformations, (Kim et al., 2010). With the broadening of eligibility criteria for cochlear implantation, a thorough and careful preoperative assessment is essential. This evaluation helps determine if the child is a suitable candidate, guides surgical planning, and informs appropriate counseling for the parents regarding expectations and outcomes. Research has demonstrated that children who undergo cochlear implantation at an early age experience notable enhancements in speech perception within one year after the procedure, outperforming those who receive implants at a later stage, irrespective of the underlying cause or the age at which the hearing loss began, (Emmett et al., 2019).

8. Conclusion

Hearing loss is a common congenital condition, affecting a significant number of newborns globally. Universal Newborn Hearing Screening plays a vital role in the early detection of hearing impairment, enabling timely medical and therapeutic intervention to support speech and language development. Although UNHS programs have contributed to earlier diagnosis and improved outcomes, continuous monitoring remains important due to the potential for progressive or late-onset hearing loss. In many low- and middle-income countries, hearing loss is more prevalent due to preventable factors like infections and exposure to harmful medications. However, in many rural and resource-limited areas, the lack of screening equipment and limited parental awareness hinder implementation. Otoacoustic Emissions (OAE) and Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR) are the most widely used electroacoustic and electrophysiological screening

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and diagnostic methods respectively for newborns. OAE is non-invasive, cost-effective, and easy to administer, making it ideal for routine screening. ABR provides detailed information on hearing thresholds and helps determine the severity and type of hearing loss. Additionally, the Auditory Steady-State Response (ASSR) offers reliable threshold estimation in infants and is less influenced by sleep, further improving diagnostic accuracy.

Audiological intervention strategies are tailored to the type and degree of hearing loss. When hearing loss is permanent and unlikely to resolve, amplification with hearing aids should be initiated early, even in mild cases. If hearing aids offer limited benefit, especially in severe to profound cases, cochlear implantation may be considered. Initially limited to children with profound bilateral hearing loss. A careful and comprehensive evaluation is essential to assess suitability for implantation, guide surgical planning, and provide effective counseling to families.

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